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γ -Cyclodextrin-graphene quantum dots-chitosan modified screen-printed electrode for sensing of fluoroquinolones

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Abstract

An innovative electrochemical approach based on screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs) modified with graphene quantum dots (GQDs) functionalized with γ -cyclodextrin (γ -CD) and assembled to chitosan (CHI) is designed for the assessment of the total content of fluoroquinolones (FQs) in animal source products. For the design of the bionanocomposite, carboxylated graphene quantum dots synthesized from uric acid as precursor were functionalized with γ -CD using succinic acid as a linker. Physic-chemical and nanostructural characterization of the ensuing nanoparticles was performed by high-

resolution transmission scanning microscopy, dynamic light scattering, Z potential measurement, Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction. Electrochemical properties of assembled bionanocomposite like potential difference, kinetic electronic transfer constant and electroactive area among other parameters were assessed by cyclic voltammetry and differential pulse voltammetry using potassium ferricyanide as redox probe. The oxidation behaviour of four representative quinolones with distinctive structures was studied, obtaining in all cases the same number of involved e^- (2) and H^+ (2) in their oxidation. These results led us to propose a single and consistent oxidation mechanism for all the checked analytes. The γ -CD-GQDs-CHI/SPCE sensor displayed a boosted electroanalytical performance in terms of linear range (4–250 μM), sensibility (LOD = 1.2 μM) and selectivity. This electrochemical strategy allowed the determination of FQs total amount in complex processed food like broths, bouillon cubes and milkshakes at three concentration levels (150, 75 and 37.5 μM) for both equimolar and different ratio FQs mixtures with recovery values ranging from 90 to 106%.

Graphical abstract

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Ethics declarations

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Supplementary Information

Below is the link to the electronic supplementary material.

[Supplementary file1 \(DOCX 2717 KB\)](#)

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